

SHAPE Project: CFD calculations for side-by-side (SBS) propulsion

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Abstract

Water depths become forbiddingly shallow to allow ship traffic in connection rivers. Propellers can damage by interacting with the riverbed under low water conditions because they are designed with the largest possible diameter for efficiency reasons. Two propellers can replace a single propeller to reduce the penetration depth of the propulsion system, with the same propeller disk area delivering similar amounts of thrust. The optimal configuration of such twin-propeller propulsion systems arranged side-by-side is investigated by computational methods simulating the flow in this project. A numerical methodology that can handle the turbulent and multiphase nature of the flow around propellers has been established. Tight side-by-side arrangements are needed to enable possible compensation of the efficiency losses due to the propeller diameter reductions by flow structure interactions. The small gaps between propellers enforced the application of the overset approach to handle rotating geometries. The accuracy of this approach is governed by the careful mesh design in the interpolation region. The application of a shell/nozzle enclosing the side-by-side propellers has been investigated. The flow interaction between the propellers shall be steered such that part of the swirling flow energy is redirected in the heading direction and generates thrust. Thereby, the performed simulations could deepen the knowledge of nozzle design for twin-propeller configurations.

1. Introduction

Extreme weather conditions, such as hotter summers, colder winters, and less distributed rain, have become more and more common in recent years. Consequentially, the amount of water carried in rivers has changed. The ship's draft must be restricted to prevent damage to the riverbed at shallow water levels [5, 17]. The draft can be reduced by limiting the ships load. Less cargo transport via inland shipping raises the overall CO₂eq emissions. Some ships can transport 3,000 tons of cargo, equivalent to 150 trucks, while road transportation generates more CO₂eq emissions than inland shipping [24]. Thus, inland vessels with a lower draft are in demand to keep low emission levels for transport even during dry periods.

Figure 1. Cargo ship in shallow water.

Figure 1 illustrates that the ship's propeller is one of the governing factors of the draft because it has to be fully submerged under water to push the vessel effectively. The thrust, T , is proportional to the quadratic velocity, V^2 , the density of the river water, ρ , and the propeller area (given by its diameter, D);

$$T \approx \rho V^2 D^2 \left[f_1 \left(\frac{ND}{V_a} \right), f_2 \left(\frac{v}{V_a D} \right), f_3 \left(\frac{gD}{V_a^2} \right) \right],$$

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where $f_{1,2,3}$ are non-dimensional relations covering the effects of the rotational speed, Reynolds number, and Froude number. Because the density is an intrinsic and unchangeable property of water and the ship shall reach its target as fast as possible, the diameter is the only free design parameter. Hence, the propellers are commonly designed with the largest possible cross-section, i.e. diameter. The diameter of the propeller defines, therefore, the draft of inland vessels.

Replacing a large propeller with two smaller propellers reduces the ship's draft¹ [17]. Preserving the thrust and the total propeller area while reducing the individual propeller diameter is challenging but possible according to the abovementioned relation. By arranging the two propellers close to each other, part of the swirling energy lost with single propellers could be recovered to improve the efficiency of multiple propellers. The generated swirl component of the individual propellers shall be converted into thrust using the fluid interactions and a surrounding nozzle guiding the flow. The occurring flow phenomena need to be understood to optimise the nozzle geometry. Propeller and nozzle optimisation is commonly performed using the blade element theory [1, 10, 19] or the lifting line method [8, 7]. However, neither method has yet been adapted to handle side-by-side propeller configurations. In this project, detailed numerical flow simulations have been carried out, revealing the flow structures and the thrust generation. The information gained from these calculations can be used for an improved blade element theory model.

2. Flow Simulation Methodology

The simulation methodology must correctly replicate turbulent flow features and cavitation in the multiphase environment [28]. Further, the rotation of the propellers needs to be represented with respect to the static geometries. The close arrangement of propellers challenges the numerical mesh generation strategy because the conventional sliding-mesh approach cannot handle such tight spacings. Another methodology is the overset grid technique [23], where the flow quantities are computed on overlapping meshes moving independently on top of each other. The connection between the grids is built by interpolating the cell and point values. The steep pressure gradients due to cavitation and the turbulent flow demand a fine mesh resolution. Therefore, the governing equations, i.e. the Navier-Stokes equations, are numerically solved with high accuracy on fine overset grids to meet the associated requirements. Such simulations require powerful computers to be accomplished in a reasonable time, which was enabled with this SHAPE project providing the resources at the VSC4.

The Vienna Scientific Cluster 4 (VSC4) consists of 790 water cooled Lenovo SD650 nodes reaching a performance (Rmax) of 2.7 PFlop/s. Each node has two Intel Skylake Platinum 8174 processors (with a nominal base frequency of 3.1 GHz) with 24 cores interconnected with 100 Gbit/s OmniPath. The standard nodes with a main memory of 96 GByte have been used for computations of this project. Because of the long calculation times of the overset mesh connectivity, only a single node has been used for the simulations. A typical computation duration of one case was between 31 and 72 days.

2.1. Description of the flow solver

For the simulation of the unsteady flow with mathematical methods, the Navier-Stokes equations were solved numerically. These consist of the conservation of mass equation

$$\frac{\partial \rho}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\rho \mathbf{u}) = 0$$

and the conservation of momentum equations

$$\frac{\partial (\rho \mathbf{u})}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\rho \mathbf{u} \mathbf{u}) = -\nabla p + \nabla \cdot \boldsymbol{\tau} + \rho \mathbf{g} = -\nabla p + \nabla \cdot \mu (\nabla \mathbf{u} + \nabla \mathbf{u}^T) + \rho \mathbf{g}$$

where t is the time, ρ is the density, \mathbf{u} is the speed, p is the pressure, $\boldsymbol{\tau}$ is the deviatoric stress tensor, μ is the dynamic viscosity and \mathbf{g} is the acceleration due to gravity.

The Crank-Nicolson scheme has been used for time integration. The gradients are calculated using a cell value-limited least squares integration scheme. All divergence operations are discretised with a second-order MUSCL scheme. All Laplace operations are solved with a linear Gaussian scheme.

¹Providing the same cross-sectional area, $A = \pi D^2/4$, and assuming no additional dimension-dependent losses, the diameter, d , with two propellers can be smaller by the factor $1/\sqrt{2}$. Or in other words, $d = 1/\sqrt{2} \cdot D = 0.707 \cdot D$.

2.2. Modelling turbulence

The viscous forces are the smallest flow scales causing the momentum dissipation, while the largest scales are the developed vortices where the flow momentum is injected. The simulation of the energy cascade in the entire range of flow scales is computationally expensive. Because the numerical effort correlates with the proportion of the flow scale spectrum resolved in the simulations, only the relevant part of the spectrum is calculated while the rest is modelled. It is possible to model only the viscous scales, which requires a very fine mesh resolution to calculate the effects of all larger scales. Coarser meshes require less computational effort, but the behaviour of turbulence needs to be modelled. This comes with higher uncertainty due to the turbulence model. In the open literature, most flow predictions around propellers are based on turbulence-modelled simulations, so-called unsteady Reynolds-Averaged Navier-Stokes (uRANS) simulations [9, 28, 26]. These have three main disadvantages:

1. Wall functions often have to be used with turbulence models so that the flow at the wall is not calculated but overwritten with empirical values. Therefore, the flow separation behaviour cannot be reliably predicted. Only the large eddies are simulated with turbulence modelling.
2. Turbulence closure models account for the flow velocity fluctuations of flow scales smaller than the mesh resolution by propagating the turbulent kinetic energy, but unresolved pressure fluctuations are neglected. Thus, not all of the force fluctuations acting on the propeller are represented in RANS simulations.
3. The modelling of turbulence by means of viscosity gives the simulated flow a laminar and more coherent behaviour. The dispersion effects due to turbulence are not included in the common models.

For the aforementioned reasons, high-resolution simulations are carried out, where at least one order of magnitude of the turbulent energy cascade is resolved. Hence, only a small proportion of the smallest turbulent scales are modelled. The high-frequency fluctuations that cannot be resolved on the numerical grid are filtered from the equations in the so-called Large Eddy Simulation (LES) approach. A so-called Favre filter, which corresponds to a density-weighted filter, is used, which is denoted in the impulse balance with an overline;

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial(\overline{\rho \mathbf{u}})}{\partial t} + \underbrace{\nabla \cdot (\overline{\rho \mathbf{u} \mathbf{u}})}_{\text{non-linear transport term}} &= -\nabla \overline{p} + \underbrace{\nabla \cdot \mu (\nabla \overline{\mathbf{u}} + \nabla \overline{\mathbf{u}^T})}_{\text{viscous term}} + \overline{\rho} \mathbf{g} + \overline{\mathbf{f}_\sigma} - \\ &- \underbrace{\left(\overline{\nabla \cdot \mu (\nabla \overline{\mathbf{u}} + \nabla \overline{\mathbf{u}^T})} - \nabla \cdot \mu (\nabla \overline{\mathbf{u}} + \nabla \overline{\mathbf{u}^T}) \right)}_{\text{unresolved viscous term}} - \underbrace{\left(\overline{\nabla \cdot (\rho \mathbf{u} \mathbf{u})} - \nabla \cdot (\overline{\rho \mathbf{u} \mathbf{u}}) \right)}_{\text{unresolved transport term}}. \end{aligned}$$

The filtering operation adds unresolved terms corresponding to the differences between the jointly and individually filtered variables. These undetermined terms originate from the non-linear transport term and the viscous term, and are modelled according to the approach of [16], whereby the symmetrical part of the unresolved stress tensor $p_{SGS} = 2/3 \rho k_{SGS}$ is added to the pressure term and the asymmetrical part representing the unresolved stresses is considered as additional subgrid dynamic viscosity $\mu_s = C_k \overline{\Delta} \sqrt{k_{SGS}}$. For the unresolved kinetic energy, k_{SGS} , an additional transport equation is solved, and the parameter C_k is calculated dynamically.

Since only flow scales smaller than the mesh resolution are modelled, the forces acting on the propeller are most accurately calculated by this method.

2.3. Multiphase flow

The density is proportionally composed of the fluids in a cell volume [15]:

$$\rho = \alpha \rho_1 + (1 - \alpha) \rho_2$$

where $\alpha = 1$ if the fluid 1 fills the volume entirely and $\alpha = 0$ if only the fluid 2 fills the volume. In the application of the propeller, the fluid 1 is the water with a density of 1000 kg/m^3 and the fluid 2 is air with the density of 1 kg/m^3 . The distribution of the volume fraction, α , is determined by the transport equation

$$\frac{\partial \alpha}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\mathbf{u} \alpha) + \nabla \cdot (\mathbf{u}_r \alpha (1 - \alpha)) = 0,$$

where $\mathbf{u}_r = \mathbf{u}_1 - \mathbf{u}_2$ is the relative velocity between the two phase velocities. Instead of calculating \mathbf{u}_r , the speed \mathbf{u}_c is set with the interface compression method and modelled by the formula [3]

$$\mathbf{u}_c = \min(C_\alpha \mathbf{u}, \max(|\mathbf{u}|)) \frac{\nabla \alpha}{|\nabla \alpha|}.$$

The constant, C_α , has the value 1. The surface tension between the two fluids separates the two-phase flow and occurs as an additional term in the conservation of momentum equations:

$$\frac{\partial(\rho \mathbf{u})}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\rho \mathbf{u} \mathbf{u}) = -\nabla p + \nabla \cdot \mu (\nabla \mathbf{u} + \nabla \mathbf{u}^T) + \rho \mathbf{g} + \mathbf{f}_\sigma,$$

where the dynamic viscosity, μ , in a control volume is proportional to the dynamic viscosities of water 10^{-6} kg/(m s) and air $1.48 \cdot 10^{-5} \text{ kg/(m s)}$

$$\mu = \alpha \mu_1 + (1 - \alpha) \mu_2.$$

The surface tension parameter, \mathbf{f}_σ , is calculated by the formula [2]

$$\mathbf{f}_\sigma = \sigma \kappa \nabla \alpha,$$

where σ represents the surface tension with the value 0.07 N/m and κ is the surface curvature [14]

$$\kappa = -\nabla \cdot \mathbf{n} = -\nabla \cdot \left(\frac{\nabla \alpha}{|\nabla \alpha|} \right).$$

The normal vector, \mathbf{n} , of the interface is determined by the normalised gradient of the volume fraction, α .

The divergence term in the transport equation for the volume fraction is discretised with the Van Leer limited Gauss scheme.

2.4. Cavitation

Propellers rotate with a screwing motion through the water, where low-pressure regions are formed on the suction side as the water is accelerated around the hydrofoil-shaped blade. The static pressure decreases the faster the propeller rotates. As the static pressure falls below vapour pressure, the water vaporises, and small gaseous bubbles or sheets are formed. This phenomenon is commonly referred to as cavitation. The collapse of cavitation bubbles or sheets may even damage the propeller. Nonetheless, cavitation occurs commonly on propellers operated near top speed, and thus, cavitation needs to be considered during the design phase of the propeller.

The cavitation model describes the growth and collapse process of vapour bubbles based on physical principles. The bubbles are already present in the bulk flow in the form of nuclei. The change in the bubble size is dependent on the surrounding conditions and can be described by the Rayleigh-Plesset equation,

$$R \frac{d^2 R}{dt^2} + \frac{3}{2} \left(\frac{dR}{dt} \right)^2 = \frac{p_b - p_{\text{sat}}}{\rho_L} - \frac{4\nu_L}{R} \frac{dR}{dt} - \frac{2\sigma}{\rho_L R}$$

where R is the radius of the bubble. For sufficiently low pressures and large pressure differences, $p_b - p_{\text{sat}}$, the Rayleigh equation

$$\frac{dR}{dt} = \sqrt{\frac{2}{3} \frac{p_b - p_{\text{sat}}}{\rho_L}}$$

can be seen as an appropriate approximation of the iso-thermal bubble dynamics. Thereby, the viscous forces and the surface tension have been neglected.

The volume fraction of the gaseous phase in the Schnerr-Sauer cavitation model [21] is computed as a function of the density and radius of the bubble and transported through the computational domain with the volume-of-fluid approach (as described in Section 2.3). The continuity equation for the liquid is adapted by an additional source term,

$$\frac{\partial \alpha_l}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\mathbf{u} \alpha_l) = \frac{\dot{m}_l}{\rho_l}$$

where \dot{m}_l is the mass transfer rate describing the phase change by

$$\dot{m}_l = \alpha_l \dot{m}_l^V + (1 - \alpha_l) \dot{m}_l^C.$$

The source terms of the mass flow rates due to condensation and vaporisation can be expressed as,

$$\dot{m}^V = -C_v (1 + \alpha_{\text{nuc}} - \alpha_l) \frac{3\rho_v \rho_l}{\rho R} \sqrt{\frac{2}{3} \frac{p_{\text{sat}} - p}{\rho_L}}, \quad p < p_{\text{sat}}$$

Figure 2. The figure illustrates graphically the discretisation process in the overset approach in a generic setup; a uniform background mesh is shown in (a), a typical rotating geometry with boundary layer refinement is shown in (b), and the merged meshes are shown in (c). (d) illustrates the identification of the (green) interpolation and (red) hole regions during the computation.

$$\dot{m}^C = -C_l \alpha_l \frac{3\rho_v \rho_l}{\rho R} \sqrt{\frac{2}{3} \frac{p - p_{\text{sat}}}{\rho_L}}, \quad p > p_{\text{sat}}$$

where the radius of the bubble core, R , and the volume fraction of the nuclei, α_{nuc} , are calculated by,

$$R = \left(\frac{3}{4\pi} \frac{\alpha_v}{1 - \alpha_v} \frac{1}{n_0} \right)^{1/3} \quad \alpha_{\text{nuc}} = \frac{V_{\text{nuc}}}{1 + V_{\text{nuc}}} = \frac{n_0 \pi d_0^3 / 6}{1 + (n_0 \pi d_0^3 / 6)}.$$

The saturation pressure, p_{sat} , is assumed to be 2300 Pa. The relaxation time coefficients, C_v and C_l , are set to 1. The number of nuclei, n_0 , is estimated as 1.6×10^{13} with a diameter $d_0 = 2\mu\text{m}$.

2.5. Discretisation of the geometry

Although moving geometries are common in mechanical engineering applications involving fluids, the numerical simulation of rotating components remains challenging. The often experienced shortcomings can be attributed to the limitations of traditional meshing methodologies. The typical strategy, splitting the domain into rotating and static meshes where sliding mesh interfaces are used to interpolate the information in between, is not suitable for configurations with close moving objects. Nonetheless, sliding meshes have been applied successfully in many propeller simulations [11, 20, 27, 9, 4, 26]. The sliding mesh approach distinguishes itself by its computational efficiency because the information is passed only on interface surfaces. Nevertheless, the connectivity of the faces on the sliding interface has to be recomputed at each time step in unsteady flow simulations.

Another methodology is the overset grid technique, where Chimera meshes are used [22]. The flow quantities are computed on overlapping meshes moving independently on top of each other. The domain connectivity information between all cells and meshes has to be computed at each time step for unsteady simulations. Therefore, the overset approach is computationally very demanding² and requires the use of high-performance computing centres such as the Vienna Scientific Cluster.

With the overset approach, all the flow information is gathered on a so-called background grid, which is shown in Figure 2 (a). The moving geometries are then equipped with a separate mesh, as shown in Figure 2 (b). The background grid and the meshes of the moving geometries can be distinguished during computation by their different cell zone numbers³. The interpolation and hole regions are initially defined when the meshes are merged and updated at every time step of the simulation. Figure 2 (d) shows the interpolation region in green and the hole region

²The computation of the domain connectivity information took about the same time as finding the flow solution for a time step.

³The mesh with the number 0 is the base mesh on which all the flow information is gathered. Thus, the background grid should be assigned with the cell zone number 0.

Figure 3. The overall computational domain is shown.

in red. The challenge of the appropriate mesh generation becomes apparent when multiple overlapping meshes are considered. For the most accurate interpolation results between meshes, the cell volumes at the interpolation region are of the same size as the cell volumes of the background mesh. Figure 2 (c) shows that this is generally the case between the rotating meshes and the background grid. However, the rotating meshes also overlap, and the interpolation region's definition becomes less straightforward. Because of the multiple overlapping meshes, the interpolation region is not necessarily located at the outer boundaries of the moving meshes but shifts to regions where essential local refinements have been performed. In such scenarios, when values from cell volumes of different sizes are interpolated on each other, the interpolation accuracy is diminished, or spurious values can occur. Thus, generating meshes with similar cell volumes is key using the overset approach and becomes a challenge, especially for three-dimensional cases. The generic test case presented in Figure 2, with two counterrotating rotors, was used as a test case to find the best setup for the interpolation algorithm and mesh cell distribution. Tang et al. [23], and Wang et al. [25] documented the calculation procedure using the overset grid technique in full detail.

As shown in Figure 3, the outer boundaries of the computational domain are a hexahedral block with an inlet, an outlet, and sides faces. The domain size ensures that the boundary conditions are applied far away from the hydrodynamic region of interest and do not degenerate the result's quality. The propellers and the nozzle are located at one-eighth of the domain length. Thereby, enough space is provided such that the flow structures can develop in the region downstream.

Figure 4 (b) shows the numerical mesh structure used for the three-dimensional propeller simulations, which has an underlying block structure. The background grid has approximately 24 million cells⁴, and each propeller mesh has approximately 2.5 million cells. The mesh resolution has been decreased towards these boundaries to allow the flow structures to leave the domain without generating spurious reflections. When the nozzle is considered, the shape can be integrated into the background mesh, where a refinement toward the surfaces is performed. The nozzle can also be considered by a static overset mesh, which facilitates the discretisation procedure but raises the computational requirements. As stated in the prior paragraph, the propeller meshes are represented by their own mesh, which allows independent rotation around a separate axis. The numerical grid must resolve the flow phenomena, particularly at the propeller edges. Thus, the numerical mesh has been refined toward the propeller surfaces to meet the criterion $y^+ < 1$, as illustrated in Figure 4 (a).

2.6. Boundary conditions

The performance curves of propellers are commonly stated as a function of the advance ratio, J ,

$$J = \frac{u_\infty}{n \cdot D},$$

where u_∞ is the freestream fluid velocity, n is the rotational speed of the propeller (given in revolutions per second), and D is the propeller diameter. The propellers are modelled as non-slip surfaces spinning around their centre axis with a rotational speed of 20 rev/s. To set the advance ratio for a simulation, the flow velocity was specified at

⁴Note that this number depends on the spacing required between the propellers and if the nozzle is included in the background grid. 24 million cells correspond to the case when the nozzle is integrated into the background grid.

Figure 4. The subfigure (a) shows the mesh on the nozzle and propellers, and a mid-plane cut is plotted in (b) illustrating the mesh structure of the background mesh with the incorporated nozzle.

the inlet and at the side faces in terms of freestream boundary conditions. A fixed flux pressure was set at the inlet and all solid surfaces, and the total pressure was specified at the outlet and sides. The pressureInletOutletVelocity is set at the outlet, which represents a zero-gradient condition for the outward flow and a fixed value condition for the inward flow.

The monitored quantities are the propeller thrust coefficient,

$$K_T = \frac{\mathcal{T}}{\rho \cdot n^2 \cdot D^4},$$

the propeller torque coefficient,

$$K_Q = \frac{Q}{\rho \cdot n^2 \cdot D^5},$$

and the propeller efficiency

$$\eta = K_T \frac{J}{2\pi \cdot K_Q}.$$

The thrust, \mathcal{T} , is determined as the sum of all forces on solid surfaces in the centre axis direction. The torque, Q , is calculated as the sum of forces acting on the propellers times the distance to their individual axis. The quantities are evaluated each tenth time-step and averaged after the initial transient settled to a steady value.

3. Results

The solver, `overInterPhaseChangeDyMFoam`, of `openFoam_v2112` has been used to obtain all the computational results. The time step has been chosen such that the CFL number is below 0.25 at all times. After the time-periodic flow field is established, five rotor revolutions have been simulated to obtain the required statistics.

3.1. Twin-propeller configurations

Possible flow interaction mechanisms between the propellers were analysed before optimising the surrounding nozzle. The first configuration considered was two parallel-arranged propellers, where five different separation distances were simulated at $J = 0.7$. The predicted thrust remained unchanged (within the numerical uncertainty, e.g. due to the inherent change of the background mesh) for all configurations, although the gap between the propeller tips was reduced below 1% of the diameter. Only minor interaction of the tip vortices shedding off the two propellers could be observed, which is in accordance with the study by Lungu [18].

Lungu [18] studied single and twin propeller arrangements via numerical simulations. The comparison of the flow field showed that the propeller tip vortex bifurcated (starting one propeller diameter downstream of itself) for the twin-propeller arrangements in contrast to the single propeller. Lungu [18] concluded that a secondary vortex of a lower strength propagates in the wake, vanishing faster than the primary tip vortex. Further, Lungu [18] noted that only the lateral velocity component was affected by the interaction, and therefore, the propulsion efficiency remained equal.

The propeller axis has been turned towards each other to enhance the flow interaction. Five configurations have been simulated at $J = 0.7$; starting from the parallel setup with step increments of 3° . Figure 5 shows that the

Figure 5. The thrust coefficient normalised by the value obtained for the parallel configuration is shown for different propeller axis inclinations towards each other. Note that only the force in the heading direction produces net thrust.

normalised thrust coefficient decreases rapidly when the propeller point toward each other and out of the heading direction. No favourable flow interaction could potentially overcome the loss due to the misalignment from the heading direction. Nonetheless, Figure 5 shows that the thrust penalty remains low for small inclination angles (of the order of the numerical uncertainty), and therefore, a configuration with a small inclination angle has been chosen for the investigation with the nozzle.

Guo et al. [9] investigated the twin-propeller performance during ship manoeuvring operations. The incident velocity distribution upstream of the propeller is affected by the ship hull's wake. The shape of the wake changes depending on the manoeuvre and general sea direction. The propeller's performance was found to be highly dependent on the position under such conditions. Therefore, it can be expected that the optimal propeller configuration is dependent on the individual ship's hull and the particular flow conditions. Such configuration can be easily investigated with the developed approach by applying a non-uniform inlet velocity distribution accordingly to the simulated or measured wake of a ship's hull.

3.2. Nozzle influence

An azimuth thruster, i.e. a shell/nozzle enclosing the propeller circumferentially, can augment the thrust at low forward travelling speeds. Thereby, the water is guided onto the propeller for improved incidence and ejected into the desired direction. The additionally provided versatility to turn the propulsor allows the direction of the resultant force into the desired direction. Thus, rudders are not needed. However, the drag of the azimuth thruster structure increases with higher flow velocities, and beneficial effects diminish under such operating conditions.

The effect of enclosing nozzles around the twin-propeller configuration on the flow structure development was investigated for several advance ratios, where the propeller axis inclination angle was kept at low inclination angles. As mentioned, the nozzle can be represented in the background grid or as an own overset mesh without movement. The thrust estimations differed by about 1% between the two discretisation strategies. The numerical evaluation of the interpolation region took about one-third longer when the nozzle was considered as an overset mesh instead of being integrated into the background grid. Thus, the nozzle geometry should be incorporated in the background grid, as shown in Figure 4 (b), for computational efficiency reasons.

Figure 6 (a) shows the time-averaged static pressure on the nozzle. The force distribution in heading direction is shown in Figure 6 (b). The blue area indicates the drag generated, whereas the red areas show a benefit for the thrust production. This information can be used for the optimisation of the shape of the nozzle. In order to understand the effect of flow interaction phenomena on thrust generation, the hydrodynamic events need to be correlated with the time series of the overall thrust generation. Such flow field correlation can be done by applying the enhanced proper orthogonal decomposition (ePOD) technique, which has been described by Hekmati et al. [13]. Enhanced proper orthogonal decomposition has been applied in many other fields correlating hydrodynamic events to sound received in the far field [12], or flame fluctuations and unsteady flow features [6]. The application of such model decomposition techniques is recommended to extend the understanding of the flow dynamics further.

Figure 6. Subfigure (a) shows the time-averaged static pressure contours on the nozzle, and the calculated thrust contribution is shown in subfigure (b).

4. Conclusion and Outlook

This SHAPE project of PRACE-6IP showed that the flow phenomena occurring with the interaction of two propellers could be replicated using numerical simulations. The flow phenomena, i.e. turbulence and cavitation, could be handled well with the applied approach. The geometrical rotation and mutual arrangement challenged the discretisation strategy. The gap between the propellers was less than 1% of the diameter and also the distance to the surrounding nozzle was small. Because the sliding-mesh strategy cannot be applied with such geometrical constraints, the overset approach has been employed. Mesh design with similar cell volumes resulted in being the most considerable challenge. Especially the thin nozzle shell close to the propellers required a reduced domain around the propellers, whereas cavitation with large pressure gradients demanded a larger domain around the propellers.

The simulated scenarios involving the twin-propeller configurations with different spacing and axis inclination toward each other did not reveal a clearly observable interaction of flow structures, which is beneficial for thrust generation. Nonetheless, the flow interaction downstream of the propellers is enhanced for tight arrangements. The thrust penalty for propeller configurations with small inclination angles was found to be low (of the order of the numerical uncertainty).

The effect of a surrounding nozzle on the flow structures could be simulated with the presented numerical methodology. The advantage of such detailed flow simulations is that regions beneficial for thrust production can be easily visualised by plotting the surface's acting forces. However, judging the impact of flow structure interaction resulted in being less straightforward and requires further in-depth investigations.

Although the overset approach limits the number of simulations due to the extortionate need for computational resources, geometrical variations of the nozzle can be easily realised (once the general meshing procedure is established). The nozzle can be added to the simulations as an additional overset mesh. Thus, everything else in the setup can be kept unchanged, while only the mesh import needs to be repeated⁵. This numerical methodology allows for easy adaptations between nozzle configurations and future optimisation depending on the ship hulls' wake.

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References

- [1] E. Benini. Significance of blade element theory in performance prediction of marine propellers. *Ocean engineering*, 31(8-9):957–974, 2004.

⁵This process involves the transformation of the mesh format into openfoam format, and the combination of the meshes into a case with the command `merge [case_folder_of_added_mesh] . -overwrite`.

- [2] J. U. Brackbill, D. B. Kothe, and C. Zemach. A continuum method for modeling surface tension. *Journal of computational physics*, 100(2):335–354, 1992.
- [3] P. Cifani, W. Michalek, G. Priems, J. G. Kuerten, C. van der Geld, and B. J. Geurts. A comparison between the surface compression method and an interface reconstruction method for the vof approach. *Computers & Fluids*, 136:421–435, 2016.
- [4] Y. Cui, W. H. Lam, H. T. Puay, M. S. Ibrahim, D. Robinson, and G. Hamill. Component velocities and turbulence intensities within ship twin-propeller jet using cfd and adv. *Journal of Marine Science and Engineering*, 8(12):1025, 2020.
- [5] Y. Cui, W. H. Lam, T. Zhang, C. Sun, D. Robinson, and G. Hamill. Temporal model for ship twin-propeller jet induced sandbed scour. *Journal of Marine Science and Engineering*, 7(10):339, 2019.
- [6] C. Duwig and P. Iudiciani. Extended proper orthogonal decomposition for analysis of unsteady flames. *Flow, turbulence and combustion*, 84(1):25–47, 2010.
- [7] B. Epps. On the rotor lifting line wake model. *Journal of Ship Production and Design*, 33(01):31–45, 2017.
- [8] B. P. Epps and R. W. Kimball. Unified rotor lifting line theory. *Journal of Ship Research*, 57(04):181–201, 2013.
- [9] H. P. Guo, Z. J. Zou, F. Wang, and Y. Liu. Numerical investigation on the asymmetric propeller behavior of a twin-screw ship during maneuvers by using rans method. *Ocean Engineering*, 200:107083, 2020.
- [10] O. Gur and A. Rosen. Comparison between blade-element models of propellers. *The Aeronautical Journal*, 112(1138):689–704, 2008.
- [11] N. Hasuike, S. Yamasaki, J. Ando, and A. Okazaki. Numerical study on cavitation erosion risk of marine propellers operating in wake flow. *Journal of the JIME*, 46(3):366–374, 2011.
- [12] A. Hekmati, D. Ricot, and P. Druault. Aeroacoustic analysis of the automotive ventilation outlets using extended proper orthogonal decomposition. In *15th AIAA/CEAS Aeroacoustics Conference (30th AIAA Aeroacoustics Conference)*, page 3347, 2009.
- [13] A. Hekmati, D. Ricot, and P. Druault. About the convergence of pod and epod modes computed from cfd simulation. *Computers & fluids*, 50(1):60–71, 2011.
- [14] J. A. Heyns and O. F. Oxtoby. Modelling surface tension dominated multiphase flows using the vof approach. In *6th European Conference on Computational Fluid Dynamics*, pages 7082–7090, 2014.
- [15] C. W. Hirt and B. D. Nichols. Volume of fluid (vof) method for the dynamics of free boundaries. *Journal of computational physics*, 39(1):201–225, 1981.
- [16] S. Huang and Q. Li. A new dynamic one-equation subgrid-scale model for large eddy simulations. *International Journal for Numerical Methods in Engineering*, 81(7):835–865, 2010.
- [17] T. Llull, A. Mujal-Colilles, and X. Gironella. Twin propeller time-dependent scouring processes. physical experiments. *Ocean Engineering*, 236:109461, 2021.
- [18] A. Lungu. Numerical assessment of twin-propeller performances. In *The 7th Conference of the Sustainable Solutions for Energy and Environment, IOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental Science*, volume 664, page 012022, 2021.
- [19] R. MacNeill and D. Verstraete. Blade element momentum theory extended to model low reynolds number propeller performance. *The Aeronautical Journal*, 121(1240):835–857, 2017.
- [20] K. J. Paik, H. G. Park, and J. Seo. Rans simulation of cavitation and hull pressure fluctuation for marine propeller operating behind-hull condition. *International Journal of Naval Architecture and Ocean Engineering*, 5(4):502–512, 2013.
- [21] J. Sauer and G. H. Schnerr. Unsteady cavitating flow—a new cavitation model based on a modified front capturing method and bubble dynamics. In *Proceedings of 2000 ASME fluid engineering summer conference*, volume 251, pages 1073–1079, 2000.
- [22] Z. Shen, D. Wan, and P. M. Carrica. Dynamic overset grids in OpenFOAM with application to KCS self-propulsion and maneuvering. *Ocean Engineering*, 108:287–306, 2015.
- [23] H. Tang, S. C. Jones, and F. Sotiropoulos. An overset-grid method for 3d unsteady incompressible flows. *Journal of Computational Physics*, 191(2):567–600, 2003.

- [24] Y. Van Fan, S. Perry, J. J. Klemeš, and C. T. Lee. A review on air emissions assessment: Transportation. *Journal of cleaner production*, 194:673–684, 2018.
- [25] G. Wang, F. Duchaine, D. Papadogiannis, I. Duran, S. Moreau, and L. Y. Gicquel. An overset grid method for large eddy simulation of turbomachinery stages. *Journal of Computational Physics*, 274:333–355, 2014.
- [26] H. Wu, Y. Ou, and Q. Ye. Numerical study on the influence of air layer for propeller performance of large ships. *Ocean Engineering*, 195:106681, 2020.
- [27] N. Yilmaz, M. Atlar, and M. Khorasanchi. An improved mesh adaption and refinement approach to cavitation simulation (marcs) of propellers. *Ocean Engineering*, 171:139–150, 2019.
- [28] M. S. Zhao, W. W. Zhao, and D. C. Wan. Numerical simulations of propeller cavitation flows based on openfoam. *Journal of Hydrodynamics*, 32(6):1071–1079, 2020.